

National Conference on Biodiversity and Plant Genetic Resource Conservation for Future

15th - 16th March, 2019

**COMPENDIUM
OF
ABSTRACTS**

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**Biodiversity and Plant Genetic
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Variability study on different local varieties of red amaranthus (*Amaranthus tricolor* L.) collected from different locations in Kerala.

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ABSTRACT

The present study entitled “Variability study on different local varieties of red amaranthus (*Amaranthus tricolor* L.) collected from different locations in Kerala” was carried out in the Department of Plant Breeding and Genetics, College of Agriculture, Vellayani during 2016-2018, with an objective to study the variability in amaranthus local varieties in terms of yield and other yield attributing characters. Thirty amaranthus local varieties were evaluated for thirteen different yield attributing traits, in which all the varieties showed different performance. The amaranthus variety collected from Kasargod district of Kerala (Madhur local) showed highest yield. The highest stem girth, petiole length and leaf width was observed in Kazhakkuttom local from Trivandrum district, Aryanadu local from

Trivandrum district showed highest internodal length, number of branches and days to 50% bolting. The study concluded that variability is the basic requirement of any crop improvement programme, so that the presence of variability in amaranthus varieties could be utilized for genetic improvement of amaranthus.

